

Redefining the Multiplication of Negative Numbers

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Abstract

In this article, I proved the new formula through the analysis of debt relationships, geometric methods, and algebraic operations:

$$z'' - a \times (-b) = zhen - en;$$

$$z'' - a \times b = ao + en;$$

$$z'' \times a \times b = zhao + en.$$

This discovery had a significant impact on the calculation method of negative number multiplication.

Keywords: Negative times negative equals positive,
Novel multiplication, Algebraic structure,
Operational axioms, Counterexample,
Extension of number systems, Sign rules,
Foundations of mathematics.

Introduction

In ancient times, people survived by borrowing food. "Debt" emerged quietly. "Less than nothing" enabled negative numbers to sprout in the soil of debt. Not long after, a wise person stipulated that "negative times negative equals positive". However, "negative times negative equals positive" puzzled countless wise people for thousands of years and made them feel perplexed about it.

Regarding the principle of "negative times negative equals positive", there are often questions:

If $-1 \times (-1) = 1$ and $-3 \times (-3) = 9$, but -1 is greater than -3 , why is the product of the larger number actually smaller?

“*Elements of algebra*”[1]has two currently most widely accepted proofs of "negative times negative equals positive":

The first proof: When $-a$ is multiplied by $+b$, the result is $-ab$. However, when $-a$ is multiplied by $-b$, the outcome cannot be the same as when $-a$ is multiplied by $+b$. Instead, it must yield the opposite result, which is $+ab$.

The second proof: Consider $(a - b)(c - d)$ expanded according to the distributive law, which equals $(a - b)c - (a - b)d$, which further simplifies to $ac - bc - ad + bd$. Here, the term " $+ bd$ " comes from $(-b) \times (-d)$. Since a negative times a negative equals a positive, the result should be $ac - bc - ad - bd$, which contradicts the above equation. Therefore, it must be " $+ bd$ ", meaning a negative times a negative equals a positive.

It is worth noting that the following content on this page of the book also states that Multiplication has been erroneously called a compendious method of performing addition.

The first proof conclusion seems somewhat difficult to convince people. The second proof conclusion was pointed out by the mathematician Felix Klein in his book “*Elementary mathematics from an advanced standpoint*”[2] that by deriving $(a-b)(c-d)$ from the formula, it leads to $(-b)(-d) = +bd$. Logically, this is actually a circular argument. Because from the very beginning, it assumed that negative numbers also follow the same operation laws as positive numbers and 0 (such as the distributive law).

Later, "*A treatise on algebra*"[3]promoted the widespread acceptance of the principle that a negative times a negative equals a positive. It established the operational laws applicable to positive integers in arithmetic algebra (including the distributive law of multiplication), which should always remain valid in symbolic algebra, even if the symbols represent negative numbers. However, it did not prove that negative numbers could apply the multiplication operation laws such as the commutative law, associative law, and distributive law.

Therefore, the principle of "negative times negative equals positive" is currently not a theorem that can be proven.

Now hold your breath. I shall begin the proof.

Proof

The first proof: Proof of debt relationship.

Assume: The initial asset balance of someone (X) is 60,000 CNY.

On the first day, (X) received 20,000 CNY as salary from the previous month and 20,000 CNY as bonus. The total asset of (X) became 100,000 CNY.

Note: 2 (20,000 CNY), 2 (20,000 CNY), 2 (type of income).

The change in (X)'s assets = initial balance + income from work = 60,000 + 40,000 = 100,000 CNY. Formula: 2×2 .

Calculation: $2 \times 2 = 4$, 4 represents 40,000 CNY of income. This is logical.

The next day, 20,000 CNY was lent to (A) and 20,000 CNY to (B) without interest. The remaining balance of (X)'s assets became 60,000 CNY.

Note: -2 (loaned out 20,000 CNY), -2 (loaned out 20,000 CNY), 2 (number of borrowers).

The change in (X)'s assets = remaining balance + loaned amount = 60000 + 40000 = 100,000 CNY. Calculation formula: -2×2 .

Calculation formula: $-2 \times 2 = -4$, -4 represents 40,000 CNY of loaned out. This is logical.

On the third day, (A) and (B) died unexpectedly with no additional assets. The remaining balance of (X)'s assets was still 60,000 CNY.

Note: -2 (loaned out 20,000 CNY), -2 (loaned out 20,000 CNY), -2 (number of deceased borrowers).

The change in (X)'s assets = original total - loaned amount = 100,000 - 40,000 = 60,000 CNY. Calculation formula: $-2 \times (-2)$.

Calculation formula: $-2 \times (-2) = 4$.

On the third day, the number 4 represents the disappearance of a loan of 40,000 CNY, but on the first day, the calculation logic of the number 4 actually represents a 40,000 CNY income.

Why does the same number have different representative meanings in logic? Could this lead to ambiguity in certain mathematical operations?

I know this sounds like heresy, but please allow me to provide proof.

First, let's forget about the original multiplication rules and assume that the results of the above calculation are all wrong. Let's see what would happen if we find a more appropriate representation for the results using the calculation formula?

Notice: The calculation formula represents the change in assets of (X) more appropriately.

To ensure that the logical meaning represented by the results of these three calculation formulas, regardless of whether they are positive or negative, is unified.

Let: The calculation formula = the change in assets of (X).

Day 1 calculation formula: $2 \times 2 = \text{Initial balance} + \text{Work income} = 6 + 2 \times 2 = 6 + 4 = 10$.

Day 2 calculation formula: $- 2 \times 2 = \text{Remaining balance} + \text{Loan amount} = 6 + 2 \times 2 = 6 + 4 = 10$.

Day 3 calculation formula: $- 2 \times (- 2) = \text{Original total amount} - \text{Loan amount} = 10 - 2 \times 2 = 10 - 4 = 6$.

The results of the three calculation formulas all represent the changes in assets, being harmonious and unified without any logical conflicts.

According to the new calculation method of the above formulas, it is noted that:

The product of positive numbers in liabilities is equal to the initial balance of assets plus the income from work. $a \times b = \text{Initial balance} + \text{Work income}$, simplified as: $zhao + en$, where zhao represents the initial balance and en represents the work income.

The negative value in the liability multiplied by the positive value equals the remaining balance of assets plus the amount of borrowed money. $- a \times b = \text{The remaining balance plus the loan amount}$ simplifies to: $ao + en$, where ao represents the remaining balance and en represents the loan amount.

The product of two negative numbers is equal to the original total amount of assets minus the amount of loans. $- a \times (- b) = \text{The original total amount minus the loan amount}$ simplifies to: $zhen - en$, where zhen represents the original total amount and en represents the loan amount.

A new formula has been derived based on the proof of debt. We should consider whether the logic expressed by the new formula is correct when it is applied in geometric analysis and algebraic operations. Before that, let's summarize the meanings of each symbol in the new formula.

Introduction to new formula symbols:

Old formula: $a \times b = a \times b$ New formula: $z''a \times b = \text{zhao} + \text{en}$

Old formula: $- a \times b = - (a \times b)$ New formula: $z''- a \times b = \text{ao} + \text{en}$

Old formula: $- a \times (- b) = a \times b$ New formula: $z''- a \times (- b) = \text{zhen} - \text{en}$

Symbols: ao, Name: concave. Meaning: In liabilities, ao represents the remaining balance, which is the remaining balance after the loan amount has been separated from the total asset amount. The name is "concave" and the symbol is "ao".

Symbols: en, Name: en. Meaning: In liabilities, en represents income from work, and it can also represent the loan amount separated from the total asset amount. The name is "en" and the symbol is "en".

Symbols: zhen, Name: zhen. Meaning: In liabilities, zhen represents the original total amount, and it is reduced by an upper limit of the original total amount. The name is "zhen" and the symbol is "zhen".

Symbols: zhao, Name: zhao. Meaning: In liabilities, zhao represents the initial balance, and it is increased by a lower limit of the initial balance. The name is "zhao" and the symbol is "zhao".

Symbols: z'', Name: z Multiplication. Meaning: Since $\text{en} = a \times b$, to distinguish the two $a \times b$ in the new formula, a "z" is added in front of the new formula. The name is "z multiplication" and the symbol is "z''".

Observation:

Old formula: $a \times b = a \times b$ follows the multiplication operation laws, including the commutative law, associative law, and distributive law.

New formula: When $\text{zhao}=0$, that is: $z''a \times b=0 + a \times b=a \times b$. The new formula can also use the multiplication operation laws of the old formula. However, at other times, the multiplication operation laws of the old formula may not be applicable to the new formula.

The second proof: Geometric analysis proof.

Note: According to the two versions of the “*The Elements of Euclid*” [4], [5] it is known that a one-dimensional number line has no width or a width of 0. The number line is a rectangle in a two-dimensional figure, and the area of the rectangle: $S = a \times b$. The width of the number line $b = 0$, so the plane area of the number line is always $S = a \times 0 = 0$. Due to the property of the zero area of the number line, the multiplication formula should be analyzed geometrically in a two-dimensional plane.

Figure 1: $z'' a \times b = zhao + en$. Let $zhao = 9$, $a = b$, and the pink grid plane diagram changes from 0 to 3.

$z'' a \times b$	=	zhao	+	$a \times b$	=	zhao + en
Let zhao	=	9	,	$a \times b$	=	en
$z'' 0 \times 0$						
zhao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 0 × 0						
$z'' 1 \times 1$						
zhao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 1 × 1						
$z'' 2 \times 2$						
zhao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 2 × 2						
$z'' 3 \times 3$						
zhao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 3 × 3						

From Figure 1, it can be seen that if zhao is a constant and a and b keep increasing, the plane will also keep expanding.

From Figure 1, it is known that if zhao is 0, the plane change of the new formula $z'' a \times b$ is the same as that of the old formula $a \times b$.

Figure 2: $z'' - a \times b = ao + en$. Let $ao = 9$, with $a = b$, and the pink grid diagram changes from 0 to 3.

$z'' - a \times b$	=	ao	+	a × b	=	ao + en
Let ao	=	9	,	a × b	=	en
$z'' - 0 \times 0$						
ao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 0 × 0						
$z'' - 1 \times 1$						
ao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 1 × 1						
$z'' - 2 \times 2$						
ao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 2 × 2						
$z'' - 3 \times 3$						
ao = 9	=		+		=	
9 + 3 × 3						

From Figure 2, it can be seen that if ao is a constant and a and b keep increasing, then the new plane after the original plane is divided will keep increasing.

From Figure 2, if $ao = 0$, the new formula $z'' - a \times b$ and the old formula $a \times b$ have the same plane variation but there is a separation distance.

Figure 3: $z'' - a \times (-b) = zhen - en$. Let $zhen = 9$, $-a = -b$, and the pink grid diagram changes from 0 to 3.

$z'' - a \times (-b)$	=	zhen	-	a × b	=	zhen - en
Let zhen	=	9	,	a × b	=	en
$z'' - 0 \times (-0)$						
zhen = 9	=		-		=	
9 - 0 × 0						
$z'' - 1 \times (-1)$						
zhen = 9	=		-		=	
9 - 1 × 1						
$z'' - 2 \times (-2)$						
zhen = 9	=		-		=	
9 - 2 × 2						
$z'' - 3 \times (-3)$						
zhen = 9	=		-		=	
9 - 3 × 3						

From Figure 3, it can be seen that if $zhen$ is a constant, and $-a$ and $-b$ keep decreasing, then the plane keeps shrinking.

From Figures 1 and 3, it can be seen that the changes in the $z''a \times b$ and $z''-a \times (-b)$ planes are opposite.

The change in the number of pink squares in the $z''a \times b$ formula in Figure 1: from $9 + 1$ to $9 + 4$ to $9 + 9$,

The change in the number of pink squares in the $z''-a \times (-b)$ formula in Figure 3: from $9 - 1$ to $9 - 4$ to $9 - 9$.

The third proof: Algebraic operation proof.

The first formula: $z''a \times b = zhao + en$, where $en = a \times b$.

Old formula: $a \times b = a \times b$.

New formula: $z'' a \times b = zhao + en$, where $en = a \times b$.

Let: $a = 1, b = 1$.

Old formula: $a \times b = a \times b = 1 \times 1 = 1$.

New formula: $z'' a \times b = zhao + en = zhao + 1$, where $en = a \times b$.

If $zhao = 0$, then $zhao + 1 = 0 + 1 = 1$, and the results of the old formula and the new formula are equal.

New formula: $0 + en =$ Old formula: $a \times b$. It can be seen that the new formula includes the old formula.

The calculation of multiplication of positive numbers by positive numbers in the old formula belongs to one of the calculations in the new formula, so no proof is needed.

The second formula: $z'' - a \times b = ao + en$, where $en = a \times b$.

Old formula: $- a \times b = - (a \times b)$.

New formula: $z'' - a \times b = ao + en$, where $en = a \times b$.

Let: $- a = -1, b = 1$.

Old formula: $- a \times b = - (a \times b) = - (1 \times 1) = -1$.

New formula: $z'' - a \times b = ao + en = ao + 1$, where $en = a \times b$.

- 1 Meaning: If the original number is 9, then -1 is the subtractor 1 in $9 - 1 = 8$, representing a state of subtracting 1 from the original number 9, emphasizing reduction.

$ao + 1$ Meaning: If the original number is 9, then $ao + 1$ is $8 + 1 = 9$, consisting of addend 8 and addend 1, representing a state of separating addend 8 and addend 1 from the original number 9, emphasizing separation.

The calculation results of the old formula and the new formula are the same, only the described states are different. Therefore, no proof is necessary.

The third formula: $z'' - a \times (-b) = zhen - en$, where $en = a \times b$.

Old formula: $-a \times (-b) = a \times b$.

New formula: $z'' - a \times (-b) = zhen - en$, where $en = a \times b$.

Let: $-a = -1$, $-b = -1$.

Old formula: $-a \times (-b) = a \times b = 1 \times 1 = 1$.

New formula: $z'' - a \times (-b) = zhen - en = zhen - 1$.

The meanings and states of the two calculation results of the old formula and the new formula are different, so a mathematical logic analysis is required.

The previous preface raised a question regarding the principle that a negative number multiplied by another negative number results in a positive number:

If $-1 \times (-1) = 1$ and $-3 \times (-3) = 9$, but -1 is greater than -3 , why is the product of the larger number actually smaller?

Let's try calculating with the new formula:

$z'' - 1 \times (-1) = zhen - 1$, $z'' - 3 \times (-3) = zhen - 9$, but $-1 > -3$.

$zhen - 1 - (zhen - 9) = zhen - 1 - zhen + 9 = 8$. The product of the larger number is finally greater than that of the smaller number.

The result of the old formula does not conform to the fact that the product of the larger number is greater than that of the smaller number.

The result of the new formula conforms to the fact that the product of the larger number is greater than that of the smaller number.

Therefore, the new formula is proven to be correct.

Conclusion

It is derived from the proof of the debt relationship that:

The product of two negative numbers is equal to the original total amount of assets minus the amount of loans.

It stems from the introduction of new formula symbols:

Old formula: $a \times b = a \times b$ follows the multiplication operation laws, including the commutative law, associative law, and distributive law.

New formula: When $zhen=0$, that is: $z''a \times b=0 + a \times b=a \times b$. The new formula can also use the multiplication operation laws of the old formula. However, at other times, the multiplication operation laws of the old formula may not be applicable to the new formula.

It stems from the proof of geometric analysis:

From Figure 4, it can be seen that when $zhen = zhao = 0$, the planes of $z'' - a \times (-b)$ and $z''a \times b$ are opposite to each other. when $zhen = zhao = 0$, when $a = b = 0, 1, \text{ or } 3$, $z'' - a \times (-b) + z''a \times b = 0 + 0, -1 + 1, -9 + 9 = 0$.

It is known from Figure 4 that when $zhen = zhao = 9$, the changes of the planes of $z'' - a \times (-b)$ and $z''a \times b$ are opposite to each other. when $zhen = zhao = 9$, when $a = b = 0, 1, \text{ or } 3$, $z'' - a \times (-b) + z''a \times b = 9 + 9, 8 + 10, 0 + 18 = 18$.

It stems from the proof of algebraic operations:

The result of the old formula does not conform to the fact that the product of the larger number is greater than that of the smaller number.

The result of the new formula conforms to the fact that the product of the larger number is greater than that of the smaller number.

Summary: The old formula $-a \times (-b) = a \times b$ only holds true under multiple stipulations in the axiomatic system. It is a reluctant compromise to maintain the consistency of the old formula in mathematical calculations.

Therefore, based on the reinterpreted rule that "negative times negative equals positive", the new formula $z'' - a \times (-b) = zhen - en$ is the true multiplication formula for negative numbers multiplied by negative numbers.

Final result: Redefine negative multiplied by negative successfully.

References

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